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IMPACT OF PSYCHOEMOTIONAL DISORDERS OF INTERCEPTOR UAV OPERATORS ON COMBAT EFFECTIVENESS: A REVIEW IN THE CONTEXT OF THE RUSSO-UKRAINIAN WAR

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Abstract. This paper examines the impact of psycho-emotional disorders and professional burnout of interceptor UAV operators on the effectiveness of their combat employment, based on the experience of the Russia-Ukraine war. The conflict has become the first in history where both sides employ UAVs on a massive scale: Russia employed up to 300 strike drones of the "Shahed" and "Geran-3" types daily during winter 2025-2026. Ukraine's response was the deployment of interceptor drones, i.e. UAVs controlled by an operator through video goggles (FPV, first person view) in real time, destroying enemy drones by mid-air collision. In 2025, over 100,000 interceptors were produced, and the number of successful interceptions exceeded 1,000 per month. However, interceptor operators experience a significantly different stress profile compared to strike UAV operators: decision time ranges from a few seconds to 40 seconds depending on target speed, with 17-25 stress episodes per night shift and 500-750 per month. Operators work in field conditions near the contact line, under direct threat, with limited nutrition options and concealment requirements. Quantitative modeling demonstrates that by the end of an 8-hour night shift, the probability of hitting the target on the first attack decreases approximately twofold (from 0.70-0.80 to 0.30-0.40), and interceptor consumption per target increases 2-2.5 times. A significant research gap was identified: no empirical studies of interceptor UAV operator mental health exist. Practical recommendations are proposed: AI-assisted

terminal guidance, optimizing shift duration (4-6 hours), psychological support, specialized field nutrition, and training adaptation.

Keywords: interceptor UAV, operator burnout, PTSD, time pressure, decision-making, Shahed, counter-drone defense, Russia-Ukraine war, combat effectiveness, human factors.

Introduction. The Russia-Ukraine war has significantly changed modern warfare through the massive scale of UAV employment. According to analysts, drones account for approximately 70% of casualties on both sides [1]. Russia employed approximately 19,000 strike UAVs during winter 2025-2026, averaging 150-200 per day [2]. Ukraine responded by deploying interceptor drones from 2024, producing over 100,000 units in 2025 [3, 4].

Despite extensive literature on UAV operator psychology (predominantly from the US context) [5, 6, 7], research on the specific stress profile of interceptor UAV operators is absent. This operator type is new and emerged during the Russia-Ukraine war. Their stressors differ significantly: extreme time pressure (5-20 seconds), repeated acute stress (500-750 episodes per month), field conditions near the contact line, and a unique source of moral injury, as a miss may lead to civilian casualties. These factors increase the risk of developing PTSD, whose symptoms such as hyperarousal and sleep disturbance directly block the ability to make rapid decisions [7].

Aim and objectives. The aim of this study is to systematize knowledge about psycho-emotional disorders of interceptor UAV operators and assess their impact on combat effectiveness. The following objectives are defined: 1) review scientific publications on the psychological consequences of UAV operator work; 2) identify the specific stress profile of interceptor UAV operators and its differences from the strike UAV operator profile; 3) develop a parametric model of interception effectiveness decline due to fatigue and stress; 4) formulate practical recommendations for maintaining operator combat readiness.

Results and discussion. A narrative review was conducted of scientific publications from Scopus, Web of Science, and PubMed databases (2014-2026) using search queries: "UAV operator stress", "drone operator burnout", "PTSD", "counter-UAS", "interceptor drone". Of 127 identified sources, 34 met the inclusion criteria. A parametric model of interception effectiveness decline was also developed based on generalized data on cognitive function impairment from peer-reviewed sources. Table 1 presents the available interception time calculation based on target UAV speed and detection range.

Table 1 - Available interception time calculation by target speed

Target UAV type	Speed, km/h	Speed, m/s	Detection range, m	T = D/V, s
Shahed-136 (Geran-2)	150-185	42-51	1500-2000	29-48
Geran-3 (Shahed-238)	300-350	83-97	1500-2000	15-24
Prospective jet UAV	400-500	111-139	1500-2000	11-18

After subtracting launch time (3-5 s) and approach (5-15 s), the operator has 14-40 s for guidance against Shahed-136, and up to 16 s against Geran-3. For prospective jet UAVs, the operator time may be under 10 s, and in some cases interception without pre-positioning becomes impossible. This justifies the need for autonomous terminal guidance for high-speed targets.

Based on generalized data on cognitive function decline [8, 9, 10, 11], a model of effectiveness decline during a night shift was constructed (Table 2).

Table 2 - Model estimate of interception effectiveness decline during a night shift

Shift hour	Kill prob. 1st attack	Interceptors/target	Miss rate, %
1-2 (start)	0.70-0.80	1.2-1.4	4-9
3-4 (mid-shift)	0.55-0.65	1.5-1.8	12-20
5-6 (fatigue)	0.40-0.50	2.0-2.5	25-36
7-8 (exhaustion)	0.30-0.40	2.5-3.3	36-49

The model shows that kill probability halves by the end of an 8-hour shift, while interceptor consumption per target increases 2-2.5 times, potentially exhausting supplies before the attack ends.

The analysis revealed a markedly different stress profile that can be defined as "chronic acute stress": repeated high-intensity episodes with extreme time pressure. Sustained hyperactivation of the nervous system under these conditions leads to rapid clinical burnout and neurobiological cognitive deficit (loss of concentration, slowed reaction), which becomes the primary cause of missed interceptions [5, 8]. This substantially differs from the "chronic monotony + episodic stress" profile documented in strike UAV operator research [5, 6]. Beyond combat stress, interceptor operators face basic survival challenges in field conditions near the contact line: threat of being hit, concealment requirements, inability to cook hot food (fire and burners reveal the position), water shortage, and malnutrition. Research shows that dehydration of just 2% of body mass and inadequate nutrition noticeably impair attention, reaction speed, and decision-making ability [11, 12, 13]. Therefore, a two-tier nutrition scheme is recommended. At the UAV unit base area, operators receive a full hot ration with heating capability. At the interception position, a compact dry ration similar to a sniper pack is used (jerky, energy bars, nuts, caffeine-containing components), requiring no heating and not compromising concealment [12]. All these factors combined reduce the effectiveness of interceptor operators. An additional factor is information overload: during mass attacks, the operator receives large volumes of data from multiple sources, requiring filtering of redundant and false information for correct decision-making under time pressure [17]. A separate factor is visual fatigue: interceptor operators control UAVs through FPV goggles or monitors [3], prolonged use of which during night shifts causes eye strain, nausea, and disorientation [11]. Russia has begun equipping Shaheds with infrared spotlights to blind interceptor pilots [3], further increasing visual stress.

AI-assisted terminal guidance of interceptor UAVs represents the most promising direction: computer vision systems relieve the operator of the most stressful task in the

final seconds of approach [3, 14]. Research confirms that AI assistance improves decision accuracy under time pressure [15].

Practical recommendations:

1) autonomous terminal guidance using AI, which improves target engagement accuracy and protects the operator from infrared spotlight blinding, since computer vision systems operate in a different spectral range;

2) limiting shift duration to 4-6 hours, which slows fatigue accumulation and maintains operator reaction speed at a level sufficient for intercepting high-speed targets;

3) psychological screening within the unit for early detection of hyperarousal symptoms and prevention of clinical PTSD development [7];

4) two-tier nutrition scheme (hot rations at base, dry rations at position), maintaining operator cognitive functions without compromising concealment;

5) training under simulated mass-attack conditions to build stress resilience and automated responses under time pressure;

6) rational distribution of effort between interceptor UAV units and EW assets [16] when planning combat employment, which reduces the total number of targets requiring interception and decreases operator workload.

Conclusions. 1. Interceptor UAV operators experience "chronic acute stress": up to 500-750 stress episodes per month, with decision time for high-speed targets not exceeding 16 seconds. This stress profile is new and has not been previously documented.

2. Quantitative modeling demonstrates approximately twofold decrease in kill probability during an 8-hour night shift and a 2-2.5 times increase in interceptor consumption.

3. A significant research gap exists: no empirical studies of interceptor UAV operator mental health have been conducted.

4. The Russia-Ukraine war experience is of practical importance for developing counter-drone defense doctrine worldwide.

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